

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTIONS WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION. PART V. ON THE EFFECT OF p_n ON THE PHOTO-REDUCTION OF MOLYBDIC ACID SOL IN UNPOLARISED LIGHT.

By J. C. GHOSH, T. BANERJEE AND MD. S. A. KEAN.

The present section deals with the effect of p on the velocity of reduction of molybdic acid sol. The reductants studied were mostly those used in the analogous reaction with tungstic acid sol.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Experimental procedure and arrangements of apparatus are exactly the same as in Part IV.

Sodium chloride of different concentrations, as formed during the process of neutralisation of acid by caustic soda for changing the p_n , was found to have no effect on the velocity of photoreductions.

Effect of p_n on the Velocity of Photoreductions.

TABLE I.

Molybdate = 0.05M. d (thickness of the cell) = 0.5 cm. I_{abs} = Intensity of energy ($366\mu\mu$) absorbed in ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

(a) Glucose = 10% Temp. = 31° $I_{abs} = 725$		(b) Leucine = 1% Temp. = 29.5° $I_{abs} = 3150$		(c) Glutamic acid = 1% Temp. = 29.5° $I_{abs} = 4275$		(d) α -Alanine = 1% Temp. = 29.5° $I_{abs} = 3420$	
p_n	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$	p_n	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$	p_n	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$	p_n	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$
1.35	3.45	0.096	3.17	1.6	1.92	1.81	1.30
2.03	3.58	1.16	3.58	1.81	2.33	2.21	2.08
2.68	3.75	1.57	5.67	2.12	3.00	2.60	2.53
3.66	3.72	1.79	7.20	2.41	3.17	3.20	2.69
4.88	3.67	2.45	8.33	3.50	3.33	4.05	2.42
5.28	3.58	3.33	8.00	4.60	2.83	4.8	2.17
5.75	1.17	4.65	7.83	5.25	2.08	5.4	1.27
		5.30	7.00	5.6	1.28		
		5.48	5.25				
		5.65	4.00				

TABLE II.

$d = 0.5$ cm. Molybdate = $0.05M$. Sodium hypophosphite = $0.083M$.
Temp. = 29.5° . $I_{abs.} = 1696$.

A. p_H	$K_{total} \times 10^{10}$, (light and dark)	$K_{dark} \times 10^{10}$, (Ka)	$K_{light} \times 10^{10}$, [$(K_t - K_a) \times 10^{10}$]	Conc. of undissociated hypophosphorous acid.					
1.63	12.08	4.67	7.42	0.0235 M					
1.81	8.75	3.50	5.25	0.019					
2.10	6.33	1.83	4.50	0.011					
3.01	4.07	0.57	3.57	0.0018					
3.94	3.43	...	3.43	0.0005					
4.7	3.33	...	3.33	...					
5.3	3.08	...	3.08	...					
5.6	1.85	...	1.85	...					
B.									
p_H	...	...	1.67	1.81	1.95	2.25	2.70	3.2	4.5
$K_{total} \times 10^{10}$ (light and dark)	...	11.80	8.75	7.00	5.67	3.85	2.18	1.02	

The data in group A have been obtained by varying the p_H by addition of caustic soda after the sol has been fully formed by the previous addition of excess of hydrochloric acid, while those in group B have been obtained with the sol prepared by adding just sufficient hydrochloric acid to the molybdate to reach a particular value of p_H . The results in group A indicate an almost constant reaction rate from p_H 2.5 to p_H 5, while those in group B indicate a steady fall with increase in p_H .

DISCUSSION.

The influence of p_H upon the velocity of photoreductions of molybdic acid sol with glucose and amino-acids is different from that with sodium hypophosphite. We shall treat the two cases separately.

Observations with Glucose and Amino-acids.

The curves in Fig. 1 when produced out the p_H axis at p_H 6.1 where the velocity of the process is expected to be nil. As the p_H decreases below 6.1, the velocity of reduction rapidly increases, the curves showing a break at p_H 4.7. The velocity of reaction increases slightly with decrease in p_H and a maximum is reached at p_H about 2.5, below which the velocity decreases very slightly.

FIG. 1.

These results are in complete agreement with the conclusions of Jander and others (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 194, 413) who found that different types of molybdic acid micelles are formed at different p_H when H^+ ions are added to an alkali molybdate.

They found that

Above p_H 6.1, the ion has the composition $(MO_4)^{-}$.

At p_H 6.1 the micelle ion $(HMO_3O_{11})^{3-}$ begins to be formed.

At p_H 4.5 the micelle ion $(HMO_5O_{21})^{5-}$ begins to be formed.

Below p_H 2.9 the micelle ion $(H_3MO_6O_{31})^{3-}$, $(HMO_{12}O_{41})^{1-}$.

$(H_7MO_{24}O_{79})^{7-}$ etc. are formed.

From our observations (*vide* Table I A; also curve with glucose, Fig. 1) on the influence of p_H upon velocity of photoreduction of molybdic acid micelle with glucose, we have seen that up to p_H 6.1, there was no reaction at all as only the ion MO_4^{2-} exists in true solution.

From our results we can rightly come to the conclusion that as the p_H is lowered below 6.1, photosensitive micelle ion $(HMO_3O_{11})^{3-}$ begins to be formed. This is complete at p_H 4.7. Beyond p_H 4.7, the micelle ion $(HMO_5O_{21})^{5-}$ which is more photo-active than $(HMO_3O_{11})^{3-}$ commences to grow and this formation is completed at p_H 2.9. Below p_H 2.9, the photo-active micelle ions $(H_3MO_6O_{31})^{3-}$, $(HMO_{12}O_{41})^{1-}$, $(H_7MO_{24}O_{79})^{7-}$ begins to appear in the system. This is why we observe a maximum in the neighbourhood of p_H 2.9 and slight decrease in velocity with further decrease in p_H .

Observations with Hypophosphite.

The results obtained with hypophosphite are somewhat different from those obtained with glucose and amino-acids. From Table II (a) it is evident that dark reaction is proportional to the concentration of undissociated hypophosphorous acid and it disappears when the concentration of undissociated hypophosphorous acid is nil. In other words, the velocity of dark reaction is given by the equation,

$$\left[\frac{dx}{dt} \right]_{\text{dark}} = K (\text{surface conc. of undissociated hypophosphorous acid})$$

The light reaction is, however, given by the equation $dx/dt = K_D (C_s \text{ dissociated reductant}) + K_V (C_s \text{, undissociated reductant})$, C_s denoting surface concentration.

The values of K_D & K_V have been calculated to be 40.8×10^{-10} and 140×10^{-10} respectively. Table III shows the validity of the equation.

TABLE III..

p_H .	Conc. of hypophosphite		$K_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^{10}$	$K_{\text{calc.}} \times 10^{10}$
	Dissociated.	Undissociated.		
1.81	0.06 M	0.019 M	5.25	5.11
2.1	0.072	0.011	4.50	4.48
3.01	0.081	0.0018	3.57	3.56
3.94	0.0825	0.0005	3.43	3.44
4.7	0.083	—	3.33	3.33

Above p_H 4.7, the entire amount of sodium hypophosphite becomes dissociated, and we have only hypophosphite ions in solution. Hence after p_H 4.7, the rate of decrease in velocity with sodium hypophosphite should be comparable with that of glucose, as has been experimentally found to be the case (*vide*, Table IV).

TABLE IV.

p_H .	$K_{\text{hypophosphite}}$	K_{glucose}	$\frac{K_{\text{hypophosphite}}}{K_{\text{glucose}}}$
4.7	3.33×10^{-10}	3.7×10^{-10}	0.90
5.3	3.08×10^{-10}	3.3×10^{-10}	0.93
5.6	1.87×10^{-10}	2.1×10^{-10}	0.90

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY,
RAMNA, DACCA.

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